

THE ECONOMIC INFLUENCE OF TSARIST RUSSIA ON THE KHIVA KHANATE: PRESSURE THROUGH TRADE AND POLITICAL INTERFERENCE

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Annotation. This article analyzes the intervention of Tsarist Russia in the internal political and economic affairs of the Khiva Khanate at the end of the 19th century, based on historical sources. Using documents and other archival materials preserved in the collection of the Ichan-Kala Museum-Reserve, the article reveals the Russian Empire's involvement in Khiva's trade system, particularly its direct influence on tax collection policies.

The article discusses the creation of trade privileges for Russian citizens, the establishment of special tax provisions for them, and the strengthening of economic control through the importation of measuring instruments (scales and weights) from Russia. Through historical documents, the article also highlights the active involvement of Russian officials in the internal policies of the Khiva Khanate in areas such as control over alcohol sales, security matters, attacks on caravans, and judicial proceedings.

Keywords: Tsarist Russia, Khiva Khanate, trade relations, taxation policy, internal policy, Russian merchants, economic influence, archival documents, Ichan Qala Museum, colonial policy, caravan safety, alcohol trade, Governor-General of Turkestan, Said Islamkhodja.

XIVA XONLIGIDA CHOR ROSSIASINING IQTISODIY TA'SIRI: SAVDO VOSITASIDAGI BOSIM VA SIYOSIY ARALASHUVLAR

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Annatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Chor Rossiyasining XIX asr oxirlarida Xiva xonligining ichki siyosiy va iqtisodiy hayotiga aralashuvi tarixiy manbalar asosida tahlil etilgan. Ichan Qal'a muzey qo'riqxonasi fondida saqlanayotgan hujjatlar va boshqa arxiv materiallari asosida Rossiya imperiyasining Xiva savdo tizimidagi ishtiroki, ayniqsa soliq yig'ish siyosatidagi bevosita ta'siri ochib berilgan.

Maqolada Rossiya fuqarolari uchun savdo imtiyozlari yaratilgani, ular uchun alohida soliq bandlari ajratilgani va o'lchov vositalarining (tarozu va toshlarning) Rossiyadan olib kinishi orqali iqtisodiy nazorat kuchaytirilgani haqida fikr yuritiladi. Shuningdek, ichkilik savdosi ustidan nazorat, xavfsizlik masalalari, karvonlarga hujumlar va sud ishlari kabi yo'nalishlarda ham Rossiya amaldorlarining Xiva xonligi ichki siyosatiga faol aralashgani tarixiy hujjatlar orqali yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Chor Rossiyasi, Xiva xonligi, savdo aloqalari, soliq siyosati, ichki siyosat, Rossiya savdogarlari, iqtisodiy ta'sir, arxiv hujjatlari, Ichan Qal'a muzeyi, mustamlakachilik siyosati, karvonlar xavfsizligi, ichkilik savdosi, Turkiston general-gubernatori, Said Islomxo'ja.

The influence of Tsarist Russia in the Khiva Khanate was evident in all spheres. The Khans of Khiva were so dependent on Russia that even their tax collection policy could not be implemented without Russian participation. In the collection of the Khiva Ichan-Kala Museum, an archival document clearly confirms this, stating that all scale weights must be sealed stones imported from the

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Russian state¹. Furthermore, the documents note that concessions were granted to Russian merchants². The documents in the collection of the Ichan Qal'a Museum-Reserve contain a specific clause regarding Russian merchants in the regulations for collecting maunat (tax) from traders, as established by Said Islomkhoja. According to this clause, a procedure for collecting taxes from Russian merchants was developed³. According to this, if Russian citizens bring and sell camels, horses, cattle, sheep, and goats to the markets of Khiva, a tax will be levied on the persons who bought them: 3 tanga for camels, 2 tanga for horses and cattle, and 0.5 tanga for sheep⁴.

The Khiva Khanate's interference in internal affairs by Tsarist Russia and its reporting on the Khan's actions are also mentioned in historical archival documents. This can be clearly seen in a letter dated April 15, 1897, written by Colonel Palkin, the governor of the Amu Darya defense⁵. The Governor-General expressed signs of friendship to the Khan of Khiva and asked him to take measures in this matter. The issue of alcohol sales in Urgench was raised when the Governor-General of Turkestan learned about the sale of vodka and other intoxicating drinks in the Urgench fortress. He assigned Palkin to investigate this information. Palkin conducted an inquiry and confirmed the veracity of the report. Subsequently, Palkin appealed to the Khan of Khiva, requesting him to issue an order to halt the activities of these two individuals. It was emphasized that after this, alcohol sales should not be permitted in Urgench⁶. This document is valuable historical evidence of the Russian Empire's policy in the Turkestan region and its influence over the Khiva Khanate.

The interference in the internal affairs of the Khiva Khanate regarding alcohol trade is substantiated in another document. The document was sent by the governor of the Amu Darya region to the chief secretary of Khiva and was written with the purpose of conveying the Russian government's order, through the Turkestan Governor-Generalship, on regulating the alcohol trade⁷.

The Governor-General of Turkestan issued Order No. 899, prohibiting the sale of vodka and wine by Russian citizens in the territory of Khiva. However, Russian citizens residing in the Urgench fortress are permitted to purchase drinks with the permission of the city mayor. The document was approved by the late Khudaybergan ibn Avazniyoz⁸. Although the sale of alcohol was restricted, Russian citizens could purchase it with the permission of the mayor⁹.

We observe cases of Russians interfering in court matters such as caravan looting and theft¹⁰. This document was one of the dialogues between the Khan of Khiva and representatives of the Russian Empire, which highlighted the territorial security of the Khiva Khanate, the attack on trade caravans, and the role of Russian military administration in this regard. This document shows that there was a problem of piracy and attacks on caravans in the territory of Khiva. The Adai Kazakhs were nomads who lived in the northern territories of the Khiva Khanate and sometimes attacked trade caravans. The Khan of Khiva asked Russian military officials for help in establishing order in his territory¹¹. This means that the Khans of Khiva received help from Tsarist Russia in many matters.

¹ Ichan Qal'a muzey qo'riqxonasi fondi. KP 3274. – B.6.

² Ichan Qal'a muzey qo'riqxonasi fondi. KP 3274.

³ Ichan Qal'a muzey qo'riqxonasi fondi. KP 3274.

⁴ Ichan Qal'a muzey qo'riqxonasi fondi. KP 3274.

⁵ Ichan Qal'a muzey qo'riqxonasi fondi. KP 3677. – B.14.

⁶ Ichan Qal'a muzey qo'riqxonasi fondi. KP 3677. – B.14.

⁷ Ichan Qal'a muzey qo'riqxonasi fondi. KP 3659.

⁸ Ichan Qal'a muzey qo'riqxonasi fondi. KP 3659.

⁹ Ichan Qal'a muzey qo'riqxonasi fondi. KP 3659.

¹⁰ Ichan Qal'a muzey qo'riqxonasi fondi. KP 3624.

¹¹ Ichan Qal'a muzey qo'riqxonasi fondi. KP 3624.

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By the end of the 19th century, the political and economic influence of Tsarist Russia on the Khiva Khanate had significantly increased. This influence was particularly evident in the trade system, tax policy, internal regulations and administration, and legal matters.

The Russian Empire gradually restricted the economic independence of the Khiva Khanate by controlling its trade activities. The requirement to import scales and weights from Russia and use only stamped weights demonstrates that Russia's activities, which outwardly appeared to be simple economic cooperation, had actually become a tool of political pressure. In particular, the inclusion of a separate clause for Russian merchants in the tax regulations developed by Said Islamkhoja proves that they were provided with special privileges.

Furthermore, the direct intervention of Russian officials in alcohol trade, judicial matters, and disciplinary issues indicates that the independent domestic policy of the Khan of Khiva was also brought under control. The restrictions on the sale of alcoholic beverages in Urgench, or allowing Russian citizens to purchase them only with special permits, demonstrate Tsarist Russia's direct interference in internal affairs.

In particular, in matters of attacks on caravans, robbery, and security, the Khivan khans sought assistance from the Russian military, which meant that the khanate was becoming militarily dependent on Russia. The dialogue of Tsarist Russia in the form of a "report" to the Khan of Khiva shows that the khanate had fallen into a de facto vassal state.

References

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